

Attachment to the Study Report:

Questionnaire Script – Interviews with Children on Ovalau Island, Fiji, 2025

Table 1: First interview guide for Loreto Catholic Primary School.

Questions:

1. What did you draw?
2. Why did you draw this?
3. Where & how did you learn about this?
4. Did you understand the questions easily, or was it hard to understand them?
5. Would you allow us to keep your drawing?
6. What can be a title for your drawing if I share it with some of your friends?
7. Do you have anything else to share with me about your drawing or yourself?

Table 2: Second interview guide for Delana Methodist Primary School.

Questions:

1. What did you draw?
2. Why did you draw this?
3. Where & how did you learn about this?
4. Would you allow us to keep your drawing?
5. What can be a title for your drawing if I share it with some of your friends?
6. When was the last time you went out fishing or catching seafood?
7. Where, who, what kind of fishing or catching activities? What types of fish and seafood, including seaweed?
8. What is the main fishing or catching activity you enjoy the most? How often do you do that? Every week or weekend, sometimes, only for special occasions?
9. What do you and your friends enjoy doing at the sea or on the beach?
10. Do you have anything else to share with me about your drawing or yourself?

Table 3: Questions used for a group discussion (talanoa) in both Primary Schools.

Note: each question is to be discussed in groups for 5-10mins

Please provide A3 papers for each group to write notes of their answers.

Questions

1. When was the last time you went out to sea? Did you go alone or with friends?
2. Do you sometimes go to the Levuka passage, also called the Natubari passage?
3. What do you usually do when you go to the Levuka/Natubari passage?
4. Are there any stories of Levuka/Natubari passages that your parents or bubu/tutu share with you?
5. What can you and your family do to better protect the sea and marine life?
6. According to you, how can underwater videos help you to protect the reef passages?

Table 4: Questions used for follow-up interviews with children.

Questions:

1. When was the first time you went out fishing?
2. Did your family celebrate the first time you went out fishing?
3. What is your favorite fishing activity/practice you enjoy/are involved in the most? Do you go out alone or with friends?
4. Where do you usually carry out that fishing activity (activities)?
5. Can you kindly describe/tell me/ show how this fishing activity is conducted?
6. What are the fishing gears that are involved in these fishing activities?
7. Is that fishing activity involved in using bait? If so, what kind of bait do you use for these fishing activities?
8. What are some of the names of the finfish you know/ usually catch when you/others go out fishing?
9. Where are these fish found?
10. What are the colors of these fish?
11. Do you sometimes go out to collect seafood? What type of seafood?
12. Do you usually collect crab? Land crabs or sea crab? Or collect small fish on low tides?
13. Where did you learn all these seafood collection skills from?
14. Have you seen or used crab traps before? Fish traps?
15. Do you enjoy going out fishing? Or is it a responsibility for you to do so?
16. What is your favorite time to go out fishing? Early in the morning, or late in the afternoon
17. How often do you go out fishing in a week/month?
18. Do you help out your family in preparing the catches? What is the main dish(es) you have?
19. What are other sea/reef-related activities that you'd prefer to do other than going out fishing?
20. How many seabirds' names do you know? Where do you commonly see them?
21. Do you go out to the farm? Who did you go out with to the farm?
22. Does your family use organic farming or chemical farming?
23. Do your parents/you sell the crops, or for family use only?
24. What happens to the marine life or the sea when chemicals are washed down from the mountains or the land on a rainy day?